

TRANSPORT PARTICLES

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Einstein's formula for the mass of a moving body assumes the existence of four types of bodies: two types with real values of mass at a speed less than the speed of light and two with different signs and an imaginary value of mass (the speed is greater than the speed of light). Interaction of temporary states of bodies allows us to consider the force of inertia as a type of interaction. At the same time, an additional real force of the temporary interaction of particles with imaginary mass was revealed. Within the framework of the new concept, it follows that at any point in the trajectory of a moving body, Newton's third law is observed. The transfer of energy at the speed of light is carried out by photons formed by two particles moving at superluminal speeds - tachyons. The transmission of impulse momentum at a speed close to the speed of light is carried out by neutrinos formed by two particles of real mass, but with different signs. The huge number of neutrinos in the world means that the amount of positive and negative energy modulo is equal to each other.

Keywords: particle models, types of interactions, transfer of physical parameters.

Introduction

More than a century ago, Einstein proposed a formula for calculating the mass of a moving body. Since then, only bodies moving at a speed less than the speed of light and a positive value of mass are considered to actually exist (Left part of Figure 1). In the time that has passed since Einstein's discovery, the

indisputability of the idea he proposed has become inevitable. However, the mathematical form of this equation inevitably leads to the possibility of the existence of four kinds of bodies (right side of Figure 1).

Figure 1: Types of Einstein solids.

The concept of the interaction of physical bodies (with positive mass) was developed by Newton – gravitation, on the basis of which a picture of the planetary scale is built. At the same time, Newton established the universal principle of equality of action and reaction on the basis of the communicative form of the gravitational equation. Recognizing this principle of Newton, let us determine the sign of the force of interaction for different types of physical bodies.

To solve the problem, it is convenient to expand the function $\text{Sign}(x)$, used in programming, into the

field of imaginary numbers. We believe that $\text{Sign}(\pm ix) = \pm i$. At the same time, let us take into account that velocity ($V = \frac{\Delta x}{ic\Delta t} = -i \frac{\Delta x}{c\Delta t}$) is an imaginary quantity, since it is the ratio of the increment of the spatial coordinate to the increment of the time coordinate (imaginary value). Table 1 shows the data for calculating the sign of the forces of interaction of Einstein's bodies according to the formula $\text{Sign}(a*b) = \text{Sign}(a)*\text{Sign}(b)$

Table 1

Signs of the forces of gravitational and electromagnetic interaction.

Type of interaction	View	Result
Static gravity		$(1*1) \cup (-1*-1)=1$ $(-1*1) \cup (1*-1)=-1$
Gravity of moving bodies		$(i*-i) \cup (-i*i)=1$ $(i*i) \cup (-i*-i)=-1$
The power of the pendant		$(i*-i) \cup (-i*i)=1$ $(i*i) \cup (-i*-i)=-1$
Ampere Power		$(-1*-1) \cup (1*1)=1$ $(-1*1) \cup (1*-1)=-1$

1 – attraction of bodies to each other, -1 – repulsion.

The table calculates the exact signs of the Coulomb and Ampere forces, assuming that the charges are physical bodies moving at a speed greater than the speed of light. The rationale for this assumption is given below. Modern ideas about the photon and neutrino give paradoxical results [1..16]

Stable photon and neutrino models

In this part, ideas are developed that make it possible to consider the types of bodies obeying Einstein's formula as real.

The main provisions relate to the role of the time coordinate

Equal time coordinate rights

1. Time intervals are calculated as imaginary values.
2. Physical objects on the time axis interact with each other
3. As in space, the interaction encompasses all states of the body on the time axis, including the future state
4. The interaction manifests itself in the absence of symmetry of temporal states—with ideal symmetry (uniform rectilinear motion of bodies according to Newton's law 1), the total interaction of temporal states is equal to zero.

Expanding the arsenal of forces

The analysis of the interaction of temporal states of physical bodies [17..21] eliminates the logical contradiction in determining the force of inertia in Newton's second law: $F = ma$

This formula is replaced by a commutative form of interaction between temporary state indicators - T

$$F_{21} = F_{12} = \frac{E}{ic\Delta t_{12}} = \frac{T_1 T_2}{ic\Delta t_{12}} [T] = \sqrt{I\kappa} \quad (1)$$

The indicator is constructed as a radical of the Einstein fraction of the bodies

$$T = \sqrt{\frac{mc^2 \Delta x}{(\Delta x)^2 + (ic\Delta t)^2}} \quad (2)$$

The resultant force is the vector sum of interactions

$$\vec{F}_r = \frac{T_{fut} T_{pr}}{ict} + \frac{T_{pas} T_{pr}}{ict} \quad (3)$$

As a result, the canonical formulas for the force of inertia have been obtained, and the postulate of the equivalence of inertial and gravitational mass, which has been tried to prove theoretically and empirically for several centuries, becomes superfluous.

In particular, when the body moves in a circle, we get

$$|F_{rep}| = - \frac{m_0 v_-^2}{R \sqrt{1 - (\frac{v_-}{c})^2}} \quad (4)$$

m_0 — mass of protoparticle,
 v_- — the speed of the physical body.

Application of the proposed method for calculating force using indicators that include the increment of time in the numerator, $T = \frac{mc^2 ic\Delta t}{\sqrt{(\Delta x)^2 + (ic\Delta t)^2}}$ leads to a force formula of the second kind. This force takes on a real value when a physical body moves at a speed greater than the speed of light – a tachyon. Thus, it is established that tachyon: 1 is an Einstein particle, 2 with its asymmetric motion along the time coordinate, a real force arises. Details of this process are given below

In particular, when such a body moves in a circle

$$|F_{attr}| = + \frac{m_0 cv_+}{iR \sqrt{1 - (\frac{v_+}{c})^2}} = + \frac{m_0 cv_+}{R \sqrt{(\frac{v_+}{c})^2 - 1}} \quad (5)$$

v_+ — the speed of a physical body exceeding the speed of light.

Pay attention to the automatically generated signs of the interaction forces: repulsion at the speed of a

body at a speed of less than the speed of light and attraction when the body moves at a speed greater than the speed of light.

In general, the formula for indicator T gives eight complex values of the indicator for four values of the root expression (two real and two imaginary). Figure 2 shows the complex values of the indicator for this set.

Figure 2. Complex multipliers of the T indicator.

In this paper, we will limit ourselves only to commutative formulas of forces obtained with the same multipliers of indicators.

Consider the motion of a tachyon along a harmonic trajectory (Figure 2)

Figure 3 Motion of a tachyon along a harmonic trajectory.

Real forces at work

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \vec{F}_{0-} \text{ Present to Past} \\
 & \vec{F}_{-0} \text{ Past to Present} , \\
 & \vec{F}_{+0} \text{ Future to the present,} \\
 & \vec{F}_{0+} \text{ Present for the future} \\
 & |\vec{F}_{0-}| = |\vec{F}_{-0}| = |\vec{F}_{+0}| = |\vec{F}_{0+}| = F = \frac{m_0 v_+}{\Delta t \sqrt{\left(\frac{v_+}{c}\right)^2 - 1}} \tag{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

The modulus of the total vector is

$$|\vec{F}_r| = 2F\Delta\alpha = \frac{2\pi v m_0 v_+}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{v_+}{c}\right)^2 - 1}} \tag{7}$$

Under the assumption of a small mass of the proto-particle, the difference between the tachyon's velocity and the speed of light - $\Delta_+ = v_+ - c \ll c$.

Then

$$|\vec{F}_r| = \frac{2\pi v m_0 v_+}{\sqrt{\frac{2\Delta_+}{c}}} \tag{8}$$

Let us note that an increase in the tachyon's velocity leads to a decrease in its charge; for example, a quark with a charge of $1/3e$ moves faster than a quark with a charge of $2/3e$.

Model of a photon in the form of two tachyons with different signs

F_r — the result of the forces of electromagnetic interaction,

F_t — the strength of the interaction of temporal states,

V_+ — The speed is greater than the speed of light.

Figure.4 Photon Model

For aesthetic reasons, the figure uses one and a half periods of oscillation of the system.

Result

1. Charge is translated from a particle property into the main characteristic of a tachyon moving at a speed exceeding the speed of light.
2. Two moving different tachyons are attracted to each other at a short distance and repel each other at a relatively long distance.
3. The latent force balances the total strength of the electromagnetic interaction of the tachyons.

1. Photon carries energy

$$E_{ph} = 2FR = + \frac{4\pi v m_0 v_+}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{v_+}{c}\right)^2 - 1}} R = hv \tag{9}$$

Photon dualism	Classic Introduction	Model
Composition	Mystical particle 	A system of two differently charged tachyons
Weight	Zero photon mass	No real mass, zero total imaginary mass
Energy	Proportional to frequency	Proportional to frequency
Motion in dielectric media	Speed reduction	Path length increases due to interaction Photon and Molecule Dipoles

The expansion of the arsenal of forces makes the possibility of the existence of Einstein particles with imaginary mass real.

The photon model explains the paradox of the presence of an electromagnetic wave produced by a particle with a zero charge value.

Neutrino model

The existence of neutrinos creates the paradox of the existence of a particle with a significant angular momentum with a very small particle mass.

Figure 5 Neutrino model

Within the framework of the proposed model, the neutrino spin is equal to

$$h \approx 2v_- R \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1-(\frac{v_-}{c})^2}} \quad (10)$$

m_0 — mass of protoparticle,
 v_- — the speed of the neutrino components, which is close to the speed of light,
 $2R$ — Mean Particle Spacing.

The force (interactions of time states) acting on the particles at the extremes of the harmonic trajectory is equal to

$$F_t = 2\pi \frac{m_0 v_-}{\sqrt{1-(\frac{v_-}{c})^2}} \nu \quad (11)$$

ν — Harmonic Frequency.

At the same time, we assume that the mass of the protoparticle is so small that the difference in velocity $\Delta_- = c - v_- \ll c$. Then

Then

$$F_t = 2\pi \frac{m_0 v_-}{\sqrt{\frac{2\Delta_-}{c}}} \nu \quad (12)$$

Note that the coincidence of the formulas for the force (8) and (12), unlike tachyons, an increase in the velocity of neutrino particles will lead to an increase in their mass

Model properties

1. The neutrino model is made up of two Einstein particles of different real masses that move at a speed close to the speed of light
2. Particles repel each other at a short distance and are attracted at a relatively greater distance.
3. The force of interaction of time states balances the net force of gravity at any point in the trajectory.
4. Neutrinos carry torque because the moments of the particles add up

$$h = 2 \frac{m_0 v_-}{\sqrt{1-(\frac{v_-}{c})^2}} R \quad (13)$$

The similarity of photon and neutrino models determines their properties, in particular, the general inverse dependence of the distance between particles on frequency.

Consequences of model structure

The paradox is resolved by constructing a model of a particle in the form of two Einstein particles differing in the **sign of real mass**

F_r — Result of gravitational forces,

F_t — The Power of Interaction of

Temporal States,

V_- — the speed is less than the

speed of light.

1. The model explains the conservation of momentum during neutron decay.

2. Neutrinos are able to transmit mechanical momentum during the translational motion of their elements.

Conclusions

1. The inclusion of the forces of interaction of temporal states in the arsenal of acting forces reveals the existence of all kinds of Einsteinian particles.

2. At any point in the trajectory of moving bodies, Newton's third law is observed.

3. The transfer of energy at the speed of light is carried out by photons formed by two tachyons

4. Momentum transfer is carried out by neutrinos formed by two particles of large mass, but with different signs.

5. The amount of positive and negative neutrino flux energy is equal to each other modulo.

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